

Effects of Urban Renewal on the Quality of Life of Residents in Katsina City, Katsina State, NigeriaAdo¹, S.; O.Y. Yahaya^{2*}; A. Yaro³ and N. Yusha, U²¹Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS)²Department of Geography, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Nigeria.³Department of Environmental Resources Management, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study assessed the impacts of urban renewal projects on the quality of life of residents in Katsina City, Katsina State, Nigeria, with emphasis on social, economic, and environmental dimensions. Data were collected from 397 respondents through a structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including factor analysis. The findings reveal that respondents were predominantly male (73%) and married (70%), with 58% attaining tertiary education. Occupations were concentrated in farming, trading, and civil service, and most respondents (60%) earned below ₦800,000 annually. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of .629 and a significant Bartlett's test ($p < .001$) confirmed the dataset's suitability for factor analysis. Seven major components, explaining 59.2% of the total variance, were extracted, representing key domains of urban renewal: infrastructure development, domestic utilities, health facilities, open spaces and parking, communication networks, environmental improvements, and socio-economic support. Perceptions of urban renewal were generally positive, with strong approval for projects addressing basic needs such as public standpipes ($M = 4.71$), clinics and primary healthcare centres ($M = 4.68$), and improved drainage ($M = 4.67$). Further results revealed strong social and economic outcomes, particularly in housing improvement ($M = 4.67$), job creation ($M = 4.59$), and income distribution ($M = 4.54$). However, environmental indicators such as air quality ($M = 2.42$) and cleanliness ($M = 2.59$) lagged significantly behind, suggesting limited ecological integration in the planning process. Overall, urban renewal interventions in Katsina City have contributed substantially to residents' quality of life through improved services, infrastructure, and livelihoods, but environmental sustainability remains a critical shortfall. The study recommends a more holistic and participatory approach that prioritizes environmental management alongside socio-economic development in future urban renewal programs.

Keywords: Urban renewal, Quality of life, Infrastructures, Sustainability, Katsina City**Introduction**

Rapid urbanization in low- and middle-income countries has shifted policy focus towards urban renewal as a means of making cities more livable, productive, and resilient. The challenges of decline and expansion that global cities face have led to the concept of urban renewal. This involves a deliberate effort to transform the urban environment through careful planning and substantial adjustments to existing urban areas, ensuring they meet both current and future needs (Roberts *et al.*, 2017). The origins of the urban

renewal programme in the United States of America can be traced back to the 1937 Housing Act, which provided for slum clearance and the replacement of dilapidated houses with subsidized public housing equipped with modern amenities (Enger & Smith, 2004). Nigeria's first urban renewal initiative began in Lagos in 1955, a response to the cholera and bubonic plague outbreaks that occurred in 1929 (Sule, 2003). According to Eni and Abua (2014), several Nigerian towns and cities have implemented

urban regeneration programs, including Calabar, Lagos, Uyo, Port Harcourt, Benin City, Akure, Makurdi, and Owerri. These urban renewal programs encompass various activities, such as the expansion, rehabilitation, construction, and dualization of urban roads. They also involve the construction and enhancement of roundabouts, the development of flyovers in cities such as Port Harcourt, Uyo, and Ibadan, as well as other urban areas, and the planting of ornamental trees, flowers, and lawns, particularly in Calabar.

Urban renewal is a crucial global strategy for addressing the pressing challenges of urbanisation, particularly in cities of the Global South. Rapid growth in these areas has consistently outstripped available infrastructure, housing, and services (Mouratidis, 2021). In Nigeria, the effects of urbanisation are alarmingly severe, with rapid urban growth resulting in informal settlements, significant congestion, and unequal access to essential amenities (Aliyu, 2017; World Bank, 2015). In response, both national and sub-national governments are vigorously pursuing renewal, housing, and infrastructure programs aimed at enhancing physical assets and driving local economic activity (Katsina State Government, 2024; UN-Habitat, 2023).

Quality of life in urban settings is a complex concept that includes both objective indicators—such as housing quality, available services, neighbourhood conditions, and accessibility—and subjective assessments, which involve people's satisfaction, sense of place, and overall well-being (Wesz et al., 2023). Research on urban renewal in Nigerian cities, such as Calabar, has shown that these initiatives can enhance transportation, improve neighbourhood aesthetics, and increase water supply, all of which contribute to a better quality of life (Eni & Abua, 2014). However, these initiatives underscore the need for participatory approaches and inclusive frameworks to ensure that the benefits of renewal are accessible to all residents. This means addressing not only infrastructural improvements but also social and psychological aspects of community life (Ameme, Weje, & Dike, 2025). In Katsina State, the government is taking decisive action to enhance physical infrastructure, improve mobility, and upgrade public facilities as key components of its urban

renewal agenda. In 2024, the state government launched extensive renewal projects, including the dualization of nine major roads and critical infrastructure enhancements, backed by a substantial budget of ₦74.5 billion (Opanuga, 2024; Naturenews.africa, 2024). These efforts demonstrate a strong commitment to transforming the urban landscape and elevating the quality of life for residents. However, despite this policy momentum, there remains a lack of empirical evidence on how these renewal initiatives translate into improvements in the quality of life for residents in the urban core of Katsina City. Research on quality of life in this region is limited, primarily focusing on issues of rural-urban migration rather than the outcomes of urban renewal (Darda'u & Umar, 2023). Furthermore, there is minimal research investigating how these renewal efforts affect different social and livelihood groups, how residents perceive the changes, and whether objective improvements in infrastructure contribute to gains in subjective well-being. This study aims to address this gap by examining the effects of urban renewal on the quality of life of residents in urban Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria, through an assessment of both infrastructural outcomes and residents' perceptions.

Study Area

Katsina City is the capital of Katsina State in northern Nigeria, located near the country's border with the Republic of Niger. It covers a total landmass of about 3,370 square kilometers and lies at approximately 12°59'20"N of the equator, and 7°36'03"E of the prime meridian (Figure 1). Built on a spur of land between the two water courses of the river Ginzo and the river Tille, which flow in a north-easterly direction, it is at the narrow neck of the water-shed between the Gada and Tagwai river basins and neighboring various local governments (Max Lock Survey Group, 1977). The city of Katsina is bounded to the north by Kaita Local Government Area; it shares borders with Batagarawa to the south and east, and with Jibia Local Government Area to the west. Katsina has a semi-arid/tropical-steppe climate with a short-wet season (roughly May/June–September, peaking in July–August) and a long dry season including the Harmattan months; mean annual rainfall is broadly in the

range of 550–800 mm depending on location and period, and temperatures are high (monthly peaks often in April). Recent regional analyses show

increasing rainfall variability and a warming trend across the Sudan savanna of Katsina State.

Figure 1: Katsina City Showing the Sampled Wards

Source: GIS Lab, FUDMA (2023)

This location in Katsina makes it a convergence point for people and socio-economic activities, stimulating urbanisation and urban redevelopment. Katsina is the region's principal urban centre and serves as the political and economic hub for multiple local government areas. (City Population, 2022)

Consequently, the various land uses are over-tuned and likely to become over-used as more people access the resources to improve their

quality of life, both objectively and subjectively. Further annexation has led to the expansion and degradation of the city center, with undesirable consequences. Hence, there is a need for urban renewal, as both the capital city and the state's primate urban center.

Materials and Methods

A multi-stage sampling technique was used in this study. The first stage involved selecting four

political wards in Katsina City with a high concentration of urban renewal activities. These wards are Gabas 1, Gabas 3, Kudu 1, and Kudu 3, all located in the Katsina Local Government Area, where urban renewal has taken place. In the second stage, two neighbourhoods from each ward were purposely selected, resulting in a total of eight neighbourhoods: Darma, Saulawa, Unguwar Alkali, Yammawa, Unguwar Madaki, Rafindadi, Sabuwar Unguwa, and Kofar Sauri. Next, a systematic sampling method was utilised to select respondents at a predetermined interval of five, following a random selection of the first respondent. Data was gathered directly from respondents through the administration of a structured questionnaire. The selected wards have a projected population of 49,288 as of 2023, and Yamane's (1967) sample size determination method was employed to calculate a total of 397 respondents. The heads of households within the sampling community served as the respondents. Data analysis was conducted using both descriptive and inferential statistical procedures, aligning with the study's objectives.

Results and Discussion

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The survey engaged 397 respondents, and the findings are summarised in Table 1. The gender distribution shows a slight predominance of males, making up 73% of the respondents, compared to 26% females. This distribution reflects the socio-economic structure of Katsina, where males are often more involved in occupations such as farming and trading, which are closely tied to urban renewal. In terms of age, the majority of respondents (55.9%) are over 36 years old, suggesting that perceptions of urban renewal are primarily shaped by mature adults with greater exposure to developmental changes. Regarding marital status, married individuals represent a significant majority at 70%, highlighting the family-oriented nature of urban participation. This finding aligns with the work of Yusha'u et al. (2021), which reported high rates of early marriage in Katsina State.

Educational attainment is relatively high, with over half (58.2%) of respondents having completed tertiary education. This indicates a population capable of critically assessing government projects. Occupationally, the respondents are primarily concentrated in farming (43.6%), trading/business (31.7%), and civil service (23.4%), ensuring that the responses reflect a diverse socio-economic background. Finally, the annual income data reveal that approximately 60% of respondents earn below ₦800,000 annually, suggesting modest livelihoods that may influence their evaluation of the benefits of urban renewal.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristic	Class	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	290	73
	Female	107	26
	Total	397	100
Age	20-35	175	44.1
	36 and above	222	55.9
	Total	397	100
Marital Status	Married	277	70
	Single	65	16.3
	Divorced	40	10
	Widowed	15	3.7
	Total	397	100
Educational Level	Qur'anic	73	18.4
	Secondary	78	19.7
	Tertiary	231	58.2
	Primary	10	2.5
	Informal	5	1.3
	Total	397	100
Occupation	Farming	173	43.6
	Trading/Business	126	31.7
	Civil Service	93	23.4
	Others	5	1.3
	Total	397	100
Annual Income	N0 – N400,000	109	27.5
	N401,000	- 127	32
	N800,000		
	N801,000	- 77	19.4
	N1,200,000		
	N1,201,000	- 47	11.8
	N1,600,000		
	Above N1,600,000	37	9.3
Total	397	100	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023

Types of Urban Renewal Projects in Katsina City

This section analyses the various types of urban renewal projects in Katsina with a focus on their impact. We present a correlation matrix that highlights the relationships among these renewal projects, and indicates whether they produce positive or negative outcomes, along with the total variance of the extracted factors, represented by the eigenvalue and the percentage of variance. The rotated factor matrix distinctly identifies the critical factors in project execution that are most influential among the renewal projects.

Perception and Implementation of Urban Renewal Projects

The results presented in Table 2 indicate that respondents have a strong perception of the implementation of urban renewal projects in Katsina, as evidenced by mean scores that predominantly exceed 4.2 on a 5-point scale. The highest-rated initiatives include public standpipes ($M = 4.71$), clinics/dispensaries/primary healthcare centres ($M = 4.68$), and improvements to drainage systems ($M = 4.67$). These ratings underscore the community's critical prioritisation of healthcare, water supply, and sanitation.

Additionally, initiatives such as roadside shops ($M = 4.59$), waste disposal facilities ($M = 4.59$), and domestic water supply ($M = 4.60$) received

high scores, reflecting their significant socio-economic and environmental impact. In stark contrast, the provision of parking lots was rated the lowest at (M = 3.76), indicating that respondents do not consider it a pressing need in comparison to other essential utilities.

The findings align with the conclusions drawn by Njoko & Okoro (2014) and Enoma & Idehen (2018), who identified the provision of social

amenities as a critical component of urban renewal projects in Nigerian cities.

Table 2: Means Analysis of Urban Renewal Projects in Katsina City.

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
i. Road construction	4.3075	.86302	397
ii. Street rehabilitation	4.4475	.68806	397
iii. Electricity connection /extension	4.5325	.64419	397
iv. Provision of Transformers	4.6125	.63903	397
v. Solar-Powered Street Light	4.5375	.77466	397
vi. Electricity-Powered Street Light	4.4250	.81611	397
vii. Domestic Water Supply	4.6025	.59192	397
viii. Provision of Public Stand Pipes	4.7150	.34473	397
ix. Waste Disposal Points/Incinerator	4.5975	.63758	397
x. Clinic / Dispensaries / PHCs	4.6825	.51707	397
xi. Provision of Parking Lots	3.7625	.38596	397
xii. Provision of Open space (green)	4.6475	.58232	397
xiii. Job opportunities (Plumbers, Electricians, etc.)	4.2950	.62987	397
xiv. Communication network (Network Masts)	4.2375	.98921	397
xv. Dredging of Urban water channels	4.4075	.84453	397
xvi. Construction and improvement of Drainage	4.6675	.47698	397
xvii. Construction of Roadside Shops	4.5925	.61023	397

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2023

Adequacy of Data for Factor Analysis

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.629, as shown in Table 2, indicates that the sampling adequacy for factor analysis is acceptable. Additionally, Bartlett’s test is significant ($\chi^2 = 750.358$, $df = 171$, $p < 0.000$), confirming that the variables are sufficiently inter-correlated to support factor analysis. This suggests that respondents’ perspectives on urban renewal projects are sufficiently coherent to be grouped into meaningful factors.

Nature of the Association Among the Types of Urban Renewal Projects

Table 4 explicitly outlines the correlation matrix for the various types of urban renewal projects under examination. The results clearly demonstrate both positive and negative correlations among the variables, confirming that

any impact on one variable will directly influence another. The variables are categorised as follows:

- X1: road construction
- X2: street rehabilitation
- X3: electricity connection/extension
- X4: provision of transformers
- X5: solar-powered street lights
- X6: electricity-powered street lights
- X7: domestic water supply
- X8: provision of open street taps
- X9: waste disposal points/incinerators
- X10: clinics, dispensaries, and primary health centres (PHCs)
- X11: construction of roadside shops
- X12: provision of parking lots
- X13: provision of open green spaces
- X14: communication networks (network masts)
- X15: dredging of urban water channels
- X16: construction and improvement of drainage systems.

These results highlight the interconnection between urban renewal initiatives and their potential mutual impacts.

The correlation matrix reveals generally weak correlations among the 16 project variables. Some projects, however, are interrelated. For example, solar-powered and electric street lights have a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.470, revealing the

strongest positive relationship between any two variables. This correlation suggests that both variables enhance the city's beauty, provide lighting, and improve public security. In contrast, many projects are independent. This observation supports the decision to conduct a factor analysis to reduce the number of dimensions and group-related interventions.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test on the Types of Urban Renewal Projects

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.629
Approx. Chi-Square	750.358
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Df	171
Sig.	.000

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023

Table 4: Correlation Matrix of the Types of Urban Renewal Projects.

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	X ₇	X ₈	X ₉	X ₁₀	X ₁₁	X ₁₂	X ₁₃	X ₁₄	X ₁₅	X ₁₆
X ₁	1.00															
X ₂	.110	1.00														
X ₃	-.083	-.002	1.00													
X ₄	.035	.105	.125	1.00												
X ₅	-.027	.065	.219	.250	1.00											
X ₆	.116	-.005	.136	.110	.470	1.00										
X ₇	.009	.186	.228	.128	.287	.081	1.00									
X ₈	.089	.135	.066	.090	.073	.026	-.045	1.00								
X ₉	-.002	.149	.090	.127	.170	.103	.252	.106	1.00							
X ₁₀	.006	.083	.057	.135	.058	.148	.045	.061	.128	1.00						
X ₁₁	.158	.070	-.060	-.011	.103	.176	-.091	.224	-.001	-.029	1.00					
X ₁₂	.087		-.060	.016	.038	.031	.014	-.097	.049	.093	-.036	1.00				
X ₁₃	.116	.248	-.033	.102	.096	.205	.028	.097	.032	.049	.098	-.006	1.00			
X ₁₄	.049	.057	.104	.071	.088	.107	-.018	.087	-.019	.050	.239	.141	.084	1.00		
X ₁₅	.096	.078	-.017	.019	.189	.275	-.021	.034	.110	.142	.256	.063	.227	.046	1.00	
X ₁₆	.200	.080	.080	.053	.085	.100	.081	-.047	-.054	.059	-.010	.082	.088	.024	.082	1.00

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Factor Analysis of Urban Renewal Projects

Table 5 indicates that seven components have eigenvalues greater than 1. Consequently, they were retained for interpretation, as per the Kaiser-

Meyer-Olkin results presented in Table 3. The factor analysis extracted seven factors, which together account for 59.2% of the variance in urban renewal projects.

Table 5: Total Variance Explained of the Types of Urban Renewal Projects
Total Variance Explained

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.953	12.208	12.208	1.783	11.143	11.143	1.755	10.970	10.970
2	1.561	9.756	21.965	.891	5.571	16.714	.718	4.485	15.456
3	1.426	8.915	30.879	.715	4.468	21.182	.585	3.656	19.112
4	1.272	7.947	38.827	.570	3.565	24.747	.560	3.500	22.612
5	1.154	7.212	46.039	.396	2.478	27.225	.486	3.037	25.649
6	1.092	6.828	52.867	.327	2.043	29.268	.468	2.927	28.576
7	1.020	6.374	59.241	.300	1.875	31.144	.411	2.568	31.144
8	.944	5.898	65.139						
9	.915	5.718	70.857						
10	.883	5.518	76.375						
11	.811	5.069	81.444						
12	.804	5.026	86.470						
13	.722	4.514	90.984						
14	.697	4.354	95.338						
15	.618	3.865	99.203						
16	.128	.797	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

Factor 1 has an eigenvalue of 1.953, accounting for 12.208% of the overall variance. This demonstrates that the first extracted factor is the most influential in explaining the variability in renewal projects. The remaining factors range from two to seven.

The analysis indicates that 59.24% of Katsina's urban renewal initiatives are attributable to these seven key factors. To determine the primary categories of urban renewal projects in Katsina City, we employed Principal Axis Factoring, followed by a Varimax rotation with Kaiser Normalization, which successfully converged in just 15 iterations, as displayed in Table 6. This rigorous analysis produced seven distinct factors, each representing a specific cluster of related renewal interventions.

Table 6: Rotated Factor Matrix for the Types of Urban Renewal Projects

		Factor						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
i.	Road construction	.632						
ii.	Street rehabilitation	.574						
iii.	Electricity connection /extension	.512						
iv.	Provision of Transformers		.670					
v.	Solar-Powered Street Light		.491					
vi.	Electricity-Powered Street Light							
vii.	Domestic Water Supply			.655				
viii.	Provision of Public Stand Pipes							
ix.	Waste Disposal Points/Incinerator							
x.	Clinic / Dispensaries / PHCs				.544			
xi.	Provision of Parking Lots				.472			
xii.	Provision of Open space					.578		
xiii.	Job opportunities (Plumbers, Electricians, etc.)							
xiv.	Communication network (Network Masts)						.606	
xv.	Dredging of Urban water channels							.507
xvi.	Construction and improvement of Drainage							

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 15 iterations.

Source: Author's Computation, 2023

The first factor reveals strong associations with road construction (0.632), street rehabilitation (0.574), and electricity connection/extension (0.512). Collectively, these elements decisively represent the critical dimension of infrastructural enhancement in urban renewal. The second factor is predominantly linked to the provision of transformers (0.670) and solar-powered streetlights (0.491), underscoring significant efforts to improve energy access and enhance urban safety through upgraded lighting.

The third factor highlights domestic water supply (0.655) as a priority, emphasizing vital interventions to ensure access to potable water and improved sanitation. The fourth factor

demonstrates a moderate but important loading on clinics, dispensaries, and primary healthcare centres (0.544), as well as on parking lots (0.472), indicating a robust focus on health services and urban service delivery. Enhanced access to healthcare and organised public spaces directly contributes to the well-being of residents and elevates the functionality of revitalized neighborhoods.

The fifth factor distinctly underscores the necessity of open spaces (0.578), reflecting essential efforts to integrate green and recreational areas into urban planning. While these initiatives significantly enhance physical and mental well-being, they remain limited in

Katsina, as evidenced by respondents' low ratings of open spaces.

The sixth factor is strongly associated with communication networks ($r = 0.606$), highlighting powerful socio-economic empowerment driven by improved connectivity and job creation. Lastly, the seventh factor emphasizes the importance of dredging urban water channels (0.507), signaling proactive measures in flood prevention and environmental sanitation. This commitment to environmental management is essential. Similar findings have been documented by Adebayo & Omole (2019) and Olamiju & Oyinloye (2015), who identify infrastructure-led renewal initiatives as the cornerstone for sustainable urban transformation in Nigerian cities.

The results clearly demonstrate that urban renewal in Katsina City is multidimensional, influencing its physical, social, economic, and environmental dimensions. The strong emphasis on infrastructure, energy, and economic dimensions reveals that although renewal efforts

are primarily development-focused, they fall short in achieving environmental balance. Furthermore, neglect of open spaces and sanitation-based projects exposes a significant gap in ecological and recreational planning that must be addressed.

Urban Renewal Projects on the Quality of Life Social/economic Indicators

Table 7 clearly demonstrates the mean distribution of responses regarding the outcomes of urban renewal projects, specifically highlighting the significant impact on social and economic indicators that enhance residents' quality of life. The social and economic outcomes are highly rated, underscoring the success of these initiatives.

Table 7: Analysis of Means of Social/Economic Indicators of Quality of Life

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis (N)
i. Improvement of Shelter	4.7075	.74302	397
ii. Health and Nutrition	4.4475	.66872	397
iii. Reduction in the Crime rate	4.5025	.79684	397
iv. Provision of Shelter	4.6725	.97581	397
v. Reduction in Vehicular accidents	4.5375	.77666	397
vi. Education and Lifelong Learning	4.4250	.58743	397
vii. Economic Wellbeing	4.8250	.21611	397
viii. Income Distribution	4.5425	.51707	397
ix. Employment Opportunities	4.5925	.51023	397

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023

Table 8: Analysis of Means of Environmental Indicators of Quality of Life

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
i. Air Quality	2.4250	.81611	397
ii. Water Quality	3.6825	.51707	397
iii. Cleanliness of the Environment	2.5925	.61023	397

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023

Social benefits related to urban renewal were ranked highly, with improvements in shelter ($M = 4.71$), provision of shelter ($M = 4.67$), and reduction in crime rates ($M = 4.50$) leading the

way. These findings suggest that urban renewal is widely perceived as a means to improve housing quality, safety, and community well-being. Additionally, education and lifelong learning (M = 4.42) are associated with increased learning opportunities resulting from these renewal efforts.

In terms of economic benefits, economic well-being (M = 4.82) received the highest rating overall, followed by employment opportunities (M = 4.59) and income distribution (M = 4.54). This data reflects a strong perception of the connection between urban renewal projects and improvements in livelihoods, job creation, and economic equity.

Environmental Indicators

The environmental impacts of the urban renewal strategies were rated as moderate, as indicated in Table 8. Water quality received a favourable rating (M = 3.68), while air quality (M = 2.42) and environmental cleanliness (M = 2.59) received much lower scores. This suggests that the environmental aspects of sustainability in Katsina's urban renewal have not been as practical as the social and economic dimensions. The results reveal a significant gap in addressing environmental challenges within the city's urban renewal effort

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study reveals that urban renewal projects in Katsina City have garnered widespread recognition and appreciation. The impact of these initiatives is evident in marked improvements in social services and economic livelihoods, particularly through enhanced access to clean water, healthcare facilities, housing, and job opportunities. These projects have undeniably played a crucial role in elevating the quality of life of residents.

However, the environmental aspects of urban renewal have been grossly overlooked. While water quality received some approval, the poor ratings for air quality and environmental cleanliness highlight a significant neglect of ecological sustainability in Katsina's urban renewal efforts. Factor analysis reveals that residents perceive urban renewal as a complex endeavour comprising infrastructure, utilities,

health, environment, and socio-economic opportunities.

The study recommends a holistic approach that effectively balances infrastructure development, social progress, and environmental protection. It is imperative to prioritize community-centred planning, foster inter-agency collaboration, and implement robust mechanisms for citizen participation. This will ensure that urban renewal programs not only address residents' needs but also promote sustainability as a core value.

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